

International Journal of Education & Applied Sciences Research (IJEASR)

ISSN: 2349 –2899 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 –4808 (Print)

Available online at:

<http://www.arseam.com>

Instructions for authors and subscription information:

<http://www.arseam.com/>

Download full paper from:

<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-1-issue-5-sep-2014-0>

BUSINESS MODEL BY SIMULATION TECHNIQUE

Sabbir Khan

Department of Mathematics

Mahatma Gandhi Engineering college, Jaipur (INDIA)

ABSTRACT-

In this paper we discussed the business and corporate linear planning model and prepare the sub model (income, current expenditure, manpower, capital expenditure, Depreciation, Financing) of different areas and discussed the numerical solution by simulation.

1. INTRODUCTION

At any point of time a business can be reviewed as a pool of funds. These funds come from variety of sources in corporate management which tried to maximize utilize the change for sustained growth of the organization A large number of researchers have worked in this direction to know the intricate structure of corporate planning vide Louis; Miller and Modgilani [3], Durand; Scott and Martin Horn [4], Alessi [1] have discussed dispersion and private property of ownership in large corporation.

Use of science in aiding management decision process evolved from the early part of the twentieth century. Over the century socio-economic conditions have gone through structural changes and to keep pace with such changes, various scientific approaches have been developed. One such phenomenal development has been the application of mathematical models in the management decision process.

The competitive and increasing demand for capital has prompted entrepreneurs and or professional managers to make best use of scarce resources the highest rate of return. It therefore necessarily implies that the decision making process is subject to alternative test keeping in view the corporate objective.

It is in this context that the concept of mathematical modeling can be appreciated. This process presupposes preparation of sub models for the different areas and formulation of a total model by a combination of the several sub models. Each of these sub models represent specialist planning process and entitle the following:

- (a) Income
- (b) Current Expenditure
- (c) Manpower
- (d) Capital Expenditure
- (e) Depreciation
- (f) Financing.

In the line of Leigh [7], Van [6], David [5], Veridge and Schechter [8] and Roy [9] to develop various sub models and a total model, and Fried [2] has given new theme of finance of simulation, which can be used as an effective tool for the

purposes of business planning? As a word of caution it should, however, be remembered that left to itself the model cannot generate any business but will enable future demands of services, pay rates, productivity, prices etc., as well as the effects upon profit, return on capital, assessment of borrowing requirements etc.

2. INCOME SUB-MODEL-

The income sub-model projects the income and may be derived as under: Let X_{ie} be the quantity produced during the year e of ith variety and be P_{ie} the price of the ith product for the period e, then the total income for the year e is given by

$$Q_e = \sum_{e=1}^j X_{ie} P_{ie}$$

3. MANPOWER SUB MODEL-

The manpower sub model, for example, is derived as follows. The number of man-hours on service/product Z is proportional to the service/product (S_z) supplied and inversely proportional to the manpower productivity (P_z), now manpower expenditure (E) proportional to man-hour wages.

$$E = \sum_{z=1}^n \frac{S_z W_z}{P_z}$$

The summation sign is to take into account of the many different services/product provided, the wage rate of various skill and different indices relating to the various skills. Here the wage inflation can be taken into account by multiplying W_z by an appropriate index.

4. DEPRECIATION SUB MODEL-

Depreciation representations the charge for use of capital assets. Although depreciation can be calculated through various methods like straight line, written down value to the ultimate objective is to realize the net capital

investment over the effective life of the asset. This methodology of realization of the costs of the capital assets is termed as 'Historical depreciation'. Changes in the value of the capital assets arising out of technological developments and or changes in the value of money. e.i., Depreciation can also be realized by way of charging a supplementary depreciation and or creation of a separate fund for the specific purpose. The depreciation calculations can be summarized by three basic equations.

(1) Gross asset value at the end of the year

$$= \text{Gross asset at the beginning of the year} + \text{additions} \\ \text{during the year} - \text{value of the assets recovered in year}$$

(2) Depreciation in year

$$= \text{Gross value of asset at the start} \times \text{depreciation rate.}$$

$$D_e = g_e \times a$$

(3) Net value of assets at the end of the year

$$= \text{Net value of assets at start of year} + \text{net capital} \\ \text{expenditure in yer} - \text{depreciation}$$

$$N_{e+1} = N_e + C_e - D_e$$

This sub model can help management to investigate quickly the effects of depreciation on various investment strategies and the consequences of making changes in the depreciation rates.

5. FINANCIAL SUB MODEL-

Through the financing sub model, the planner can translate the implications of various alternative plans in terms of income, expenditure, capital requirement, etc. and there effects upon interest, borrowing, profit, return on capital etc. The main input and output variables of the sub model are:

Q_e = Income

I_e = Interest

E_e = Working expenses

C_e = Capital requirement

B_e = Borrowing

D_e = Depreciations

NA_e = Net asset

L_e = Inflationary depreciation

ROC_e = Return on capital

SFR_e = Self financing ratio

t_e = Interest rate

Income from the services rendered by an organization meets to cover to some extent both working expenditure and capital requirements of the organization. Working expenditure includes the wages and salaries of operative staffs, clerical staff, general administrative staff and cost of all maintenance work. Working expenditure thus represents money following out of the business, i.e., negative cash flow. The capital required by corporation for investment in capital plant is provided partly by its own resources and partly from borrowing money from Govt. with an appropriate rate of interest.

In mathematical terms the condition that the sum of money flowing into the business must be equal to the flowing out plus increase in current assets is recognized as a continuity equation and expressed in the form:

$$Q_e + b_e = C_e + E_e + I_e$$

Loans from govt. are at fixed rates. A number of such loans will be current in any one year and if we assume an average interest rate for one year the total interest paid on loans in any year e is given by

$$I_e = \sum_{q=s}^{e-1} t_q B_q + f(B_e)$$

The term $f(B_e)$ refers to the fact that borrowing may start at any time during the year and not necessarily at the end ; thus interest is payable for part of the year in which the loan is initiated. For practical purposes it is acceptable to assume that $f(B_e)$ is directly proportional to the interest paid in a full year.

Therefore $f(B_e) = r t_e B_e$

Now we have

$$I_e = I_{e-1} + r B_e t_e + (1-r) B_{e-1} t_{e-1}$$

Now the profit in year e is written as:

$$P_e = Q_e - E_e - D_e - L_e - I_e$$

An important factor to consider in measuring the financial performance is the value of its assets. A critical measure of performance is the capacity generally defined as the ratio of return to asset value expressed as a percentage,

$$\frac{\text{Return}}{\text{Asset Value}} \times 100\%$$

So, $ROG_e = \frac{Q_e - E_e - D_e}{(NA_e + NA_{e-1})/2} \times 100\%$

Another important indicator to the planner is the degree to which the organization is financing its investment out of its own resources. This indicator is the self financing ratio SFR_e and is defined as:

$$SFR_e = \frac{P_e + D_e + L_e}{C_e} \times 100\%$$

But we have, $P_e = Q_e - E_e - D_e - L_e - I_e$

So
$$SFR_e = \frac{Q_e - E_e - I_e}{C_e} \times 100\%$$

$$= \left(\frac{C_e - B_e}{C_e} \right) \times 100\%$$

$$= \left(1 - \frac{B_e}{C_e} \right) \times 100\%$$

By the above equations financial implications of alternative strategies can readily be evaluated.

6. TARIFF DECISIONS-

A facility, which is of particular interest to applied mathematicians, is that provided for the evaluation of tariff policies, since it illustrates mathematical programming in practice.

The basic aim of a tariff policy is to achieve a return on investment sufficient to meet the needs of the business whilst charging a fair price to its customers. With this aim constantly in mind it is, therefore, necessary from time to time revise tariffs and despite a consistently high record of improved productivity over the year it is occasionally necessary, in times of particularly high cost inflation, to revise these tariffs upwards.

Moreover, it is not practicable to change tariffs when only small increases in income are required. A method was, therefore, needed to translate the additional income requirement into forecasts of when tariff increase should be planned and what the magnitudes of these increases should be.

Let us consider that all tariff changes occur at the beginning of a year. Let Z_e be the additional income required in year e over that originally forecast.

Let Y_e be the income from a change in tariff in year e and a_e the rate of growth of the business in the same year. This latter is relevant because a change in tariff which initially produces an income of Y_e per annum will in the next year produce an income of $a_{e+1}Y_e$.

In general a tariff change in year 'e' giving a change in income of Y_e in that year will produce a change in income in year U .

$$Y_e a_{e+1}, a_{e+2}, \dots, a_u = \frac{Y_e R_u}{R_e}$$

Where $R_e = \prod_{v=1}^e \gamma_v$

The change in income from a tariff change in any one year is restricted to fixed increment changes i with some minimum changes, k_i

$$Y_e \in \{0, \pm(Zi, \pm(z+1)i, \dots, \pm ij)\}$$

Where i and z are integers. The restriction on the interval between tariff changes is expressed by introducing zero-one dummy variable, δ_e such that,

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_e &= 1 \text{ if there is a tariff change in year } e, \\ &= 0 \text{ otherwise,} \end{aligned}$$

If tariff changes cannot occur less than M years apart, then we must also have

$$\sum_{U=0}^{M-1} \delta_{e+U} \leq 1 \text{ for all } e.$$

The choice of optimizing function is somewhat arbitrary. The tariff steps should be chosen to produce an income as near to the required income as possible. One method could be to minimize the squared deviations from the required income. In this case the problem can be specified as,

$$\text{Minimize } \sum_{e=1}^N (K_e - \sum_{U=1}^e \delta_U Y_U \times \frac{R_e}{R_U})^2$$

$$\text{Subject to } \sum_{U=0}^{M-1} \delta_{e+U} \leq 1 \text{ for } e = 1, 2, \dots, N.$$

The tariff problem requires decisions on tariffs in each year e . If the best tariff policy to choose in year e depends on earlier decisions only in that they affect the total income at the start of year t , the problem can be split into a hierarchy of problems of the form: what is the best policy to choose in year e , if the income at the start of year e is ' r '. If the best policy to choose in year $e+1$ for any given income level ' r ' at the start of year $e+1$ is known, then the problem reduces to calculating the effect of making a certain tariff change in year e and following the best policy in later years. Mathematically, let $C(r, e)$ be the value of

the optimum tariff policy with income ' r ' at the start of year e , that is $C(r, e)$ is the sum of squared differences for year $e, e+1, \dots, j$. Then if tariff changes may occur one year apart $C(r, e)$ is defined by,

$$C(r, e) = \min. \{V_e(e, \beta) + C(\beta, e+1)\}$$

Where $v_e(r, \beta)$ = the square difference in year e of an increase in income from 'r' to b in that year = $(Z_e - B)^2$.

The above equation is solved for years $e = N, N-1, \dots, 2$ in order and (B-rs) gives the optimum tariff in each year.

7. NUMERICAL SOLUTION-

The inputs in the table-7.1 and table-7.2 of an organization have been given and the management wishes to examine the financing implications for the organization.

Table-7.1

Year e	Income Q	Working Expenditure E	Capital Requirement C	Depreciation		Mean Net Assets A	Interest Rates% t
				D	L		
1	1100	700	700	180	75	3860	9
2	1350	750	760	200	90	4400	9
3	1500	800	800	220	105	4970	9
4	1650	900	850	250	120	5560	9
5	1900	1000	900	280	135	6170	9
6	2100	1100	950	310	150	6800	9
7	2300	1250	1000	340	165	7450	9
8	2500	1400	1100	370	190	8145	9
9	2800	1550	1200	400	205	8910	9
10	3100	1700	1300	430	220	9745	9

Table: 7.2

Year	Borrowing (B)	Profit (P)	Interest (T)	ROC (%)	SFR
1	490.1(-)	45.1	190.1	5.70	29.99
2	392.6	77.4	232.6	9.09	48.34
3	368.5	106.5	268.5	9.66	53.93
4	404.1	75.9	304.1	8.99	52.46
5	339.9	145.1	339.9	10.05	62.23
6	321.3	168.7	371.3	10.15	66.18
7	352.5	142.5	402.5	9.53	64.75
8	438.2	101.8	438.2	8.96	60.17
9	428.7	166.3	478.7	9.54	64.28
10	418.3	231.7	518.13	9.95	67.80

Table-7.3

Year	Borrowing	Profit	Interest	ROC%	SFR	Income	Capital Requirement
1	279.1	165.9	183.7	11	60.13	1304.6	700
2	286.4	183.6	210.4	11	62.31	1434.0	760
3	270.4	204.6	237.1	11	66.21	1566.7	800
4	250.5	229.5	262.1	11	70.52	1761.6	850
5	226.6	258.4	285.3	11	74.82	1958.7	900
6	198.2	291.8	306.2	11	79.13	2158.0	950
7	164.9	330.1	324.4	11	83.51	2409.5	1000
8	175.0	365.0	340.9	11	84.10	2666.0	1100
9	178.0	417.0	358.1	11	85.17	2930.1	1200
10	173.4	476.6	375.3	11	86.66	3202.0	1300

In this example we use the financing sub model equations year by year starting from the first year and once the borrowing levels and the interest charges for any year have been calculated the remaining equations can be solved. In this case we assume that the management wants a return on capital for each year would be 11% and the typical output from financing sub model will be in the table 7.3:

It is most unlikely that the first plan to be evaluated by the model is satisfactory in all respects, satisfying simultaneously the various business targets and constraint and management will want to ask a number of questions. These will be likely to take the form of “what must I change to achieve such and such return on capital, or such and such a self financing ratio, or to keep borrowing within such and such limit?” Any one of these targets could be met or constraints satisfied by varying income, working expenditure or capital requirements either singly or simultaneously. In practice, income is allowed to vary while all other inputs are held constant and one of the out put is specified. This only approximately represents what is practicable but in view of long lead times on capital expenditure, it is sufficiently realistic to be acceptable for experimental purpose. Moreover, it provides a useful estimate, which a new plan may be built.

8. REFERENCE

- [1] De,Alessi –Private property &dispersion of ownership in large corporation, jr. of finance18 (1973).
- [2] Weston J. Freid, - New theme of finance in simulation system, jr. of finance,29(1974).
- [3] Miller M.H, &Franco Modgilani, -Cost of capital to electric utility industry; American economic Review, 56 (1966).
- [4] Durand David, -cost of debt and equity funds for a business; change problem & measurements, reprinted in management of corporate capital edited Esgha Solomen Free press, New York,(1959).
- [5] Scott David, Jr & John D. Martin,-Industrial influence on financial structure; financial management,4(1975).
- [6] Horn, Van, J.C,-Fundamentals of financial management, Printcen Hall,(1977).
- [7] Leigh,J.R,- Modelling principle & simulation; modeling of dynamic system,Vol.1 Edited H. Mcholaon,(1980).
- [8] Veridged GDC, Schechte, R.A, - Optomalization-theory & Practice, McGraw Hills.
- [9] Roy, S., -On a non-linear programming of a economic development of a developing country; Pure & Applied Mathematical Science, Vol 6, (1977).